

Dicarboxylato Derivatives of (Cyclopentadienyl, Methylcyclopentadienyl)Titanium(IV)

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Dicarboxylato derivatives of (cyclopentadienyl, methylcyclopentadienyl)titanium(IV) of the type $(C_5H_5)(CH_3C_5H_4)Ti(O_2CR)_2$ ($R = -CH_2Cl, -CHCl_2, -CCl_3, -CH_3, -C_2H_5, -C_3H_7, \text{ or } -C_6H_5$) have been prepared in aqueous as well as nonaqueous media by the reaction of $[(C_5H_5)(CH_3C_5H_4)]TiCl_3$ with the respective sodium carboxylates. These complexes have been characterised by elemental analyses, molecular weight determinations, conductivity measurements, ir and 1H nmr spectroscopy. The carboxylato ligands have been found to be monodentate in the complexes where $R = -CH_2Cl, -CHCl_2, -CCl_3$, whereas in the other complexes they are chelating bidentate. Moreover, cyclopentadienyl and methylcyclopentadienyl rings are not identically pentahapto in the complexes where the carboxylato ligands are bidentate.

COMPLEXES of the type $(C_5H_5)_2Ti(O_2CR)_2$ were prepared by refluxing Cp_2TiCl_2 with silver or alkali metal carboxylates in THF, benzene or acetone¹⁻⁵. Nesmeyanov *et al.*^{6,7} prepared $Cp_2Ti(O_2CCF_3)_2$ and discussed the bonding of carboxylato ligand. Brainina *et al.*⁸ prepared mono-, di- and trihaloacetates of the type $Cp_2M(O_2CR)_2$ where $M = Zr$ or Hf , in which the carboxylato groups were monodentate.

The present communication deals with the preparation and characterisation of dicarboxylato derivatives of the type $[(C_5H_5)(CH_3C_5H_4)]Ti(O_2CR)_2$ where $R = -CH_2Cl, -CHCl_2, -CCl_3, -CH_3, -C_2H_5, -C_3H_7$ or $-C_6H_5$.

Experimental

Well dried and purified samples of C_5H_5 , CH_2Cl_2 , $CHCl_3$, THF and petroleum ether (60-80°) were used as solvents. $PhNO_2$ for conductivity measurements was purified as described by Fay and Lowry⁹. Pure sodium acetate and benzoate were commercially available whereas sodium salts of other carboxylic acids were prepared by precipitation on mixing equivalent amounts of NaOH in alcohol and appropriate carboxylic acid in benzene. $[(C_5H_5)(CH_3C_5H_4)]TiCl_3$ was prepared¹⁰ by the reaction of $(CH_3C_5H_4)Ti$ on $(C_5H_5)TiCl_3$ in THF and the product was recrystallised from $CHCl_3$.

Preparation of the complexes :

(A) *In aqueous medium* : To an aqueous solution of $[(C_5H_5)(CH_3C_5H_4)]TiCl_3$ (prepared by refluxing 1 g of the compound in 50 cm³ water for

30 min ; pH adjusted to 1.2 by HCl), was added an aqueous solution (10% ; 10 cm³) of $ClCH_2COONa$ dropwise with constant stirring. The orange red precipitate obtained was extracted in CH_2Cl_2 (5 × 10 cm³). The combined extract was dried over anhydrous $CaCl_2$ and concentrated *in vacuo* to 10 cm³. Petroleum ether (60-80°) was added to the concentrate dropwise with constant stirring and the resulting orange red precipitate was collected and dried *in vacuo*. Recrystallisation from $CHCl_3$ gave orange red $[(C_5H_5)(CH_3C_5H_4)]Ti(O_2CCH_2Cl)_2$ in ~ 90% yield.

(B) *In nonaqueous medium* :

$[(C_5H_5)(CH_3C_5H_4)]TiCl_3$ (1.315 g ; 0.005 mole) was refluxed with anhydrous $ClCH_2COONa$ (1.16 g ; 0.01 mole) in THF (50 cm³) for 8-10 hr. The reaction mixture was cooled and filtered to remove NaCl. The filtrate was concentrated *in vacuo* to 10 cm³. To the concentrate was added petroleum ether (60-80°) dropwise with constant stirring and the resulting orange red precipitate was collected and dried *in vacuo*. Recrystallisation from $CHCl_3$ gave orange red $[(C_5H_5)(CH_3C_5H_4)]Ti(O_2CCH_2Cl)_2$ in ~ 95% yield.

Other carboxylato derivatives were prepared by similar methods.

Physico-chemical measurements :

IR spectra in the region 4000-250 cm⁻¹ (in KBr) were recorded on Perkin Elmer Model-621 grating spectrophotometer. 1H NMR spectra were recorded in $CDCl_3$ on Perkin Elmer R-32 spectrophotometer at a sweep width of 900 Hz using TMS as an internal standard. Molecular weights were

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determined ebullioscopically in benzene and conductivity measurements were carried out in PhNO₂ using Beckman R-18 conductivity bridge.

Results and Discussion

The carboxylato derivatives reported herein have been prepared by the reaction

(where R = -CH₂Cl, -CHCl₂, -CCl₃, -CH₃, -C₂H₅, -C₃H₇ or -C₆H₅). These complexes are orange red to orange yellow in colour. They are soluble in organic solvents such as CHCl₃, C₆H₆, CS₂ and CH₃COCH₃ but insoluble in water and petroleum ether. The solubility increases as the carbon chain in alkyl part of the carboxylato ligand gets bulkier. On refluxing [(C₅H₅)(CH₃C₅H₄)]Ti(O₂CR)₂ (where R = -CH₃, -C₂H₅, -C₃H₇ or -C₆H₅) with FeCl₃ for 3 hr in THF and evaporating the reaction mixture to dryness under reduced pressure, a residue is obtained. The residue is extracted in petroleum ether and the extract on evaporation to dryness under reduced pressure gave a solid which on sublimation yielded pure (C₅H₅)₂Fe

The product, (C₅H₅)₂Fe, is identified by ¹H nmr spectrum (τ value 4.7 in CCl₄) and also by elemental analysis. (Found : C, 64.9 ; H, 5.4 ; Fe, 30.4. Calcd. for (C₅H₅)₂Fe ; C, 64.51 ; H, 5.37 ; Fe, 30.11%).

Moreover, on refluxing [(C₅H₅)(CH₃C₅H₄)]Ti(O₂CR)₂ with water in THF for 1 hr, cyclopentadienyl group gets knocked off and an oxybridge compound [(CH₃C₅H₄)Ti(O₂CR)₂]₂O containing only CH₃C₅H₄ ring is obtained

The oxybridge compound was identified by ir spectrum (strong band at ~ 690 cm⁻¹) and by elemental analysis. (Found : C, 47.8 ; H, 5.2 ; Ti, 19.2. Calcd. for [(CH₃C₅H₄)Ti(O₂CCH₃)₂]₂O ; C, 47.43 ; H, 5.13 ; Ti, 18.97%).

¹H NMR spectra :

The ¹H nmr spectra of dicarboxylato derivatives reported herein indicate four distinct resonances, (i) a sharp signal due to C₅H₅ ring protons, (ii) a broad multiplet due to CH₃C₅H₄ ring protons, (iii) a sharp signal due to the protons of CH₃ group of CH₃C₅H₄ and (iv) signal or signals due to the protons of alkyl or aryl part of carboxylato ligand. In case of acetato, monochloroacetato, dichloroacetato and benzoato derivatives, a sharp signal each due to -CH₃, -CH₂Cl, -CHCl₂ and -C₆H₅, respectively is obtained. A symmetrical quartet for -CH₃ protons (as a result of splitting of -CH₃ singlet due to adjacent -CH₂ group) and a triplet due to CH₂ protons (as a result of splitting of CH₂ singlet due to adjacent CH₃ group) are exhibited for propionato derivative, whereas a triplet, a sextet and a triplet due to -CH₂, -CH₂- and -CH₃ protons, respectively are obtained for butyrato derivative. The integrals of the different resonances are in good agreement with the chemical formulae of these complexes. The proton chemical shifts are given in Table 2.

IR spectra :

The absorption bands appearing in the ir spectra of these complexes are given in Table 3. The assignments are made according to Fritz¹¹.

Nakamoto¹² has explored the possibilities of bonding of acetate ion to a metal atom as follows :

TABLE 1—ELEMENTAL ANALYSES, MOLECULAR WEIGHTS AND CONDUCTIVITY DATA FOR [(C₅H₅)(CH₃C₅H₄)Ti(O₂CR)₂]

R	Molar conductivity ohm ⁻¹ cm ² mole ⁻¹	Concentration mM	Molecular weight Found/(Calcd.)	Analysis% ; Found/(Calcd.)				m.p. °C	Colour
				C	H	Cl	Ti		
CH ₂ Cl	0.79	0.5	394 (979)	46.1 (47.5)	4.1 (4.2)	19.4 (18.7)	12.8 (12.66)	120	Orange red
CHCl ₂	0.78	0.6	469 (448)	39.2 (40.2)	3.2 (3.1)	32.0 (31.7)	11.0 (10.7)	130	Yellow orange
CCl ₃	0.77	0.5	540 (517)	33.4 (34.8)	2.2 (2.8)	40.7 (41.2)	9.2 (9.3)	140	Yellow orange
OH	0.76	0.5	330 (310)	57.2 (58.06)	5.9 (5.8)	—	15.9 (15.5)	125	Orange yellow
C ₂ H ₅	0.78	0.6	355 (328)	59.2 (60.35)	6.4 (6.5)	—	13.9 (14.2)	115	Orange yellow
C ₃ H ₇	0.76	0.7	380 (366)	61.4 (62.3)	7.2 (7.1)	—	12.9 (13.1)	110	Orange yellow
C ₆ H ₅	0.78	0.6	456 (434)	70.8 (69.1)	5.2 (5.07)	—	10.6 (11.06)	108	Orange yellow

TABLE 2—PROTON CHEMICAL SHIFT* IN CDCl_3 FOR $[(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)_2(\text{CH}_2\text{C}_2\text{H}_4)_2\text{Ti}(\text{O}_2\text{CR})_2]$

R	C_2H_5 Ring protons	$\text{CH}_2\text{C}_2\text{H}_4$ Ring protons	CH_2 Protons of $\text{CH}_2\text{C}_2\text{H}_4$	R or carboxylato ligand and J values in Hz	Ratio of integrals	
CH_3Cl	-630	-608	-207	$-\text{CH}_3$ -383	5 : 4 : 3 : 4	
CHCl_3	-594	-567	-198	CH -540	5 : 4 : 3 : 2	
CCl_4	-621	-612	-189	—	5 : 4 : 3	
OH_2	-576	-554	-185	OH_2 -110	5 : 4 : 3 : 6	
C_2H_5	-576	-554	-185	$-\text{CH}_3$ -99(t) J=7Hz	$-\text{CH}_2$ -207(q) J=7Hz	5 : 4 : 3 : 10
C_2H_7	-576	-554	-185	$-\text{CH}_3$ -86(t) J=7Hz	$-\text{CH}_2$ -144(s) -198(t) J=7Hz	5 : 4 : 3 : 14
C_6H_5	-621	-594	-194	$-\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$ -698	5 : 4 : 3 : 10	

t=triplet ; q=quartet ; s=sextet ; * in Hz.

TABLE 3—VIBRATIONAL FREQUENCIES (in cm^{-1}) AND THEIR ASSIGNMENTS FOR CARBOXYLATO COMPOUNDS

R= CH_3	C_2H_5	C_2H_7	C_6H_5	CH_2Cl	CHCl_3	CCl_4	Assignment
(a) For $(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)_2(\text{CH}_2\text{C}_2\text{H}_4)_2\text{Ti}(\text{O}_2\text{CR})_2$							
8105 m, b	8105 m, b	8105 m, b	8105 m, b	8105 m	8105 m	8105 m	C-H (Ring stretching)
2905 w	2905 w	2905 w	2905 w	2905 w	2905 w	2905 w	C-H Stretching (CH_3 part of $\text{CH}_2\text{C}_2\text{H}_4$)
2840 w	2845 w	2845 w	—	2840 w	2825 w	—	C-H Stretching (alkyl part of carboxylato ligand)
1405 s	1400 s	1405 s	1405 s	1410 s	1405 s	1405 s	O-C (Ring stretching)
1030 m, b	1025 m, b	1045 m, b	1025 m, b	1025 m	1030 m	1025 m	C-H (Ring deformation)
1345 w	1345 w	1345 w	—	1345 w	1345 w	—	C-H Alkyl part of carboxylato (deformation)
785 b	785 b	815 b	810 m, b	795 s	815 s	805 s	C-H Ring out of plane bending
—	—	—	710 m	—	—	—	C-H Out of plane stretching for aromatic part of carboxylato ligand
1530 s	1525 s	1530 s	1530 s	1660 s	1660 s	1670 s	O-C-O Antisymmetric stretching (ν_2)
1435 s	1425 s	1440 s	1485 s	1325 s	1320 s	1370 s	O-C-O Symmetric stretching (ν_1)
95	100	90	95	335	340	300	($\nu_2 - \nu_1$)
(b) For $\text{Na}(\text{O}_2\text{CR})$							
1578 s	1560 s	1565 s	1550 s	1590 s	1605 s	1640 s	O-C-O Antisymmetric stretching (ν_2)
1414 s	1410 s	1405 s	1400 s	1410 s	1420 s	1450 s	Symmetric stretching (ν_1)
164	150	160	150	180	185	190	($\nu_2 - \nu_1$)

v=very ; s=strong ; b=broad ; w=weak ; m=medium ; sh=shoulder.

In assigning the structure to the carboxylato derivatives reported herein ionic structure (I) has been rejected on the basis of conductivity data (Table 1), as the carboxylato derivatives having ionic structure (I) are expected to show conductivity of higher order.

For deciding between the remaining three modes of linkage, i.e. unidentate (structure II), chelating bidentate (structure III) and bridging bidentate (structure IV) of the carboxylato ligand to the metal atom, ir spectral study is important. Curtis¹⁴ and Nakamoto^{1,2} have discussed in detail the modes of linkage for acetato complexes. For free acetate ion^{1,4} (in NaOAc, solid, ionic), the symmetrical (ν_1) and antisymmetrical (ν_2) O-C-O stretching frequencies are 1414 and 1578 cm^{-1} , respectively. The separation, ($\nu_2 - \nu_1$) is 164 cm^{-1} . In the complexes with unidentate acetate groups^{1,2,18} (structure II), ν_2 (antisymmetrical O-C-O stretching fre-

quency) increases whereas ν_1 (symmetrical O-C-O stretching frequency) decreases. As a result, the separation between the two ($\nu_2 - \nu_1$) is much larger in such complexes than in the free acetate ion. In the case of complexes with chelating bidentate ligands^{1,2,18} (structure III), the opposite trend is observed i.e. ν_2 decreases and ν_1 increases. Therefore, the separation ($\nu_2 - \nu_1$) is smaller than that for the free acetate ion. In the case of complexes with bridging^{1,8} bidentate acetate (structure IV) ν_2 and ν_1 both increase almost to the same extent and thus the separation ($\nu_2 - \nu_1$) is closer to that for free acetate ion.

In the present investigation the differences ($\nu_2 - \nu_1$) for acetato, propionato, butyrato and benzoato derivatives have been observed to be 95, 100, 90 and 95 cm^{-1} , respectively. This difference in these complexes is much smaller than the one in the corresponding free carboxylate ion

(164, 150, 160 and 150 cm^{-1} , respectively). Therefore, a chelating bidentate structure (III) is proposed for acetato, propionato, butyrato and benzoato complexes. On the other hand the $\nu_2 - \nu_1$ differences for monochloro-, dichloro- and trichloroacetato derivatives have been observed to be 335, 340 and 300 cm^{-1} , respectively and the separation $\nu_2 - \nu_1$ is much larger than that of corresponding free carboxylate ion (180, 185 and 190 cm^{-1} , respectively). Therefore a unidentate structure (II) is assigned to monochloro-, dichloro- and trichloroacetato complexes. Bridging bidentate linkage (structure IV) has been rejected as in the complexes having such structure ν_1 and ν_2 both increase to almost the same extent so as to give $\nu_2 - \nu_1$ of the same order as that observed for the free carboxylate ion, but in the complexes investigated herein such a trend has not been observed. Moreover, the molecular weights (Table 1) indicate these complexes to be monomers, which is unlikely if bridging mode (structure IV) is involved.

As compared to the ir spectrum of $[(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)_2(\text{CH}_3\text{C}_2\text{H}_4)]\text{TiCl}_2$, C-H out of plane bending at 785-810 cm^{-1} , C-H ring deformation at 1025-1045 cm^{-1} and C-H ring stretching at 3105 cm^{-1} are very broad in case of acetato, propionato, butyrato and benzoato derivatives. This broadening as well as the reactions (a) and (b) in which cyclopentadienyl ring is knocked off, clearly indicate that cyclopentadienyl ring is loosely bonded to titanium as compared to methylcyclopentadienyl ring, in the carboxylato derivatives in which the carboxylato ligand is bidentate.

Had there been identically bonded pentahaptocyclopentadienyl and pentahaptomethylcyclopentadienyl rings in these complexes, it would have been a 20 electron system (12 electrons contributed by C_5H_5 and $\text{CH}_3\text{C}_2\text{H}_4$ rings and 8 electrons by two bidentate carboxylato groups) which is unlikely. In literature, there is evidence for the existence of two different types of linkage for even the same type of ring in a particular compound. For instance, Cotton *et al*¹⁵, on the basis of crystallographic studies, explained that in $(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)_4\text{Ti}$, the two cyclopentadienyl rings are pentahapto while the remaining two rings are monohapto thus giving 16 electron system (12 electrons contributed by two pentahapto rings and 4 electrons by two monohapto rings).

In the present complexes of the type $[(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)_2(\text{CH}_3\text{C}_2\text{H}_4)]\text{Ti}(\text{O}_2\text{CR})_2$ (where R = $-\text{CH}_3$, $-\text{C}_2\text{H}_5$, $-\text{C}_3\text{H}_7$ or $-\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$) by analogy to the above discussion^{2,5}, methylcyclopentadienyl ring is penta-

hapto, whereas loosely bonded cyclopentadienyl ring may be monohapto or trihapto (as shown below) leading to 16 or 18 electron systems, respectively (6 electrons contributed by pentahaptomethylcyclopentadienyl ring, 2 or 4 electrons by monohapto- or trihapto-cyclopentadienyl ring respectively and 8 electrons by two bidentate carboxylato groups).

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